

Solution of Rank Deficient Normals

L Lindegren 1981 Sept 24

Poder (1981 Aug 17) has derived an algorithm for computing the pseudo-solution of rank deficient normal equations. The following is an alternative (simpler?) derivation of a very similar algorithm. It is found to be a variant of Greville's algorithm.

Suppose we have a system of normal equations of order n and rank $r < n$. It is possible to find a permutation of the unknowns such that the upper-left (r,r) -submatrix is positive definite. (Proof?) Thus we write the normals in block form

$$\begin{array}{l} r \\ n-r \end{array} \left\{ \begin{array}{cc} \left(\begin{array}{cc} A & a \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} x \\ y \end{array} \right) = \left(\begin{array}{c} f \\ g \end{array} \right) \\ \left(\begin{array}{cc} a' & \alpha \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} y \\ \end{array} \right) \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

$\underbrace{\hspace{2em}}_r \quad \underbrace{\hspace{2em}}_{n-r} \quad \underbrace{\hspace{1em}}_1 \quad \underbrace{\hspace{1em}}_1$

where A and α are symmetric and A^{-1} exists. Since the rows of A are linearly independent, the same is true for the rows of $(A \ a)$, i.e. the first r rows of the normal equations matrix. Since the latter is of rank r , it follows that the last $n-r$ rows, i.e. $(a' \ \alpha)$, can be written as linear combinations of the first r rows. If a solution to (1) exists, the elements of g must be the same linear combinations of the elements of f . Consequently we need only consider the subsystem of (1),

$$Ax + ay = f, \quad (2)$$

the remaining equations, $a'x + \alpha y = g$, being linear combinations of (2).

Eqn (2) can be solved for x in terms of y ,

$$x = A^{-1}(f - ay) = p - qy, \quad (3)$$

where $p = A^{-1}f$ and $q = A^{-1}a$. It is seen that $\begin{pmatrix} p - qy \\ y \end{pmatrix}$ is a solution to (1) for any vector y .

Among the infinitude of solution vectors, we select the one with minimum norm, i.e. the pseudo-solution. Thus y is chosen to minimize

$$s = \begin{vmatrix} x \\ y \end{vmatrix}^2 = x'x + y'y = p'p - 2y'q'p + y'q'qy + y'y. \quad (4)$$

Since

$$\frac{\partial s}{\partial y} = -2q'p + 2q'qy + 2y \quad (5)$$

the minimizing y is obtained by solving the system of order $n-r$,

$$(I_{n-r} + q'q)y = q'p. \quad (6)$$

The process is readily extended to any number of right-hand sides (m). An algorithm for the pseudo-solution is indicated in the attached figure.

The algorithm is strongly reminiscent of the Greville algorithm for recursive computation of the Moore-Penrose inverse C^+ of an arbitrary matrix C of rank > 0 :

Define $C = (C_1 \ C_2)$. Set $D = C_1^+ C_2$ and $E = C_2 - C_1 D$.

If $E \neq 0$, set $B = E^+$, otherwise set $B = (I + D'D)^{-1} D' C_1^+$.

Then

$$C^+ = \begin{pmatrix} C_1^+ - DB \\ B \end{pmatrix}.$$

By recursion this algorithm reduces the computation of the M-P inverse of C to the computation of M-P inverses of column vectors. The M-P inverse of column vector V is $V^+ = 0$ if $V = 0$; otherwise, $V^+ = (V'V)^{-1} V'$.

We can apply Greville's algorithm to find the M-P inverse of $(A \ a)$. Since $A^+ = A^{-1}$ we have $D = A^{-1} a = q$ and $E = a - AA^{-1} a = 0$; consequently $B = (I + q'q)^{-1} q' A^{-1}$ and

$$(A \ a)^+ = \begin{pmatrix} A^{-1} - q(I + q'q)^{-1} q' A^{-1} \\ (I + q'q)^{-1} q' A^{-1} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

Comparison with (6) and (3) shows that our pseudo-solution is precisely

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = (A \ a)^+ f. \quad (8)$$

The M-P inverse of the full normal equations matrix is easily obtained by applying Greville's algorithm to the partitioning $C_1 = (A \ a)'$, $C_2 = (a' \ \alpha)'$, and using $C_1^+ =$ transpose of (7). The result is

$$\begin{pmatrix} A & a \\ a' & \alpha \end{pmatrix}^+ = \begin{pmatrix} A^{-1} - A^{-1}qSq' & -qSq'A^{-1} + qSq'A^{-1}qSq' & A^{-1}qS - qSq'A^{-1}qS \\ S q'A^{-1} - Sq'A^{-1}qSq' & Sq'A^{-1}qS \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where $S = (I + q'q)^{-1}$. This can be factored as

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} A & a \\ a' & \alpha \end{pmatrix}^+ &= (I - qSq' \quad qS)' A^{-1} (I - qSq' \quad qS). \quad (10) \\ &= (A \ a)^+ (I - qSq' \quad qS) \\ &= (A \ a)^+ A \begin{pmatrix} A \\ a' \end{pmatrix}^+ \end{aligned}$$